

ISSN: 3026-8370

GAMJI

JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY LEGAL STUDIES

VOL 1 - ISSUE 1 | JAN - JUN, 2024

A PUBLICATION OF

GAMJI INSTITUTE FOR TRAINING
AND RESEARCH

GAMJI

JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY LEGAL STUDIES

VOL 1, ISSUE 1

JANUARY – JUNE, 2024

ISSN 3026-8370

**A PUBLICATION OF
GAMJI INSTITUTE FOR TRAINING AND RESEARCH
BAUCHI STATE,
NIGERIA
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**This Journal can be cited as:
Gamji Journal of Contemporary Legal Studies, 1(1)
ISSN:3026-8370, 2024**

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THE NIGERIAN JUVENILE JUSTICE SYSTEM: IMPLEMENTATION, CHALLENGES AND THE WAY FORWARD

By

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13126958

ABSTRACT

Nigerian Juvenile Justice System plays a crucial role in addressing the needs and rights of young offenders within Nigeria's criminal justice system, with a focus on fairness, rehabilitation, and promoting the well-being and reintegration of young people in conflict with the law. This study provides an in-depth Analysis of the Nigerian Juvenile Justice System and Its Implementation; it examined the legal frameworks, implementation, challenges, and potential avenues for reform. The Nigeria's juvenile justice system is governed by Children and Young Person Law (1958) and the Child Rights Act (2003) which has been domesticated in all the states of the federation. Coexistence of Native and Western-inspired laws poses challenges in balancing cultural traditions and human rights principles. The implementation of the Nigerian Juvenile Justice System faces significant challenges due to the lack of adequate institutional support and resources. Insufficient funding, limited infrastructure, poor monitoring and supervision, and a shortage of trained personnel hinder the effective functioning of the system and its ability to provide appropriate interventions to young offenders. The research employed doctrinal research methodology, primarily relying on the analysis and interpretation of legal sources. The study identified and analyzed relevant laws, including the Child Rights Act, Administration of Criminal Justice Act, case laws, judicial pronouncements, and other legislation specific to juvenile offenders. The findings revealed that the existing legal frameworks are not effectively implemented, with corruption and a lack of accountability being widespread within the system. Furthermore, there is inadequate provision of healthcare, education, and recreational facilities in juvenile detention centers. The study recommends increased budgetary allocation and infrastructure development for juvenile justice institutions. Specialized training programs for personnel are needed, and monitoring/oversight mechanisms should be strengthened to promote accountability.

Keywords: Juvenile, delinquency, Justice, Juvenile Justice, Child Right, Implementation

1. INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian Juvenile Justice System plays a crucial role in promoting the well-being, development and reintegration of young offenders. However, juvenile delinquency is a significant problem in Nigeria. The most Common delinquencies are theft, assault and drugs. Additionally, poverty, child labor, family issues, peer pressure, lack of education and recreation contribute to youth crime. Nigeria's juvenile justice system bears the imprint of its British colonial roots. This system aspires to address juvenile delinquency through a framework that prioritizes both fairness and rehabilitation.¹ It is primarily governed by the Children and Young Person Act 1958² and the Child's Rights Act, 2003.

The system navigates between native and western-inspired laws, reflecting Nigeria's cultural diversity. Native laws emphasize community resolutions and restorative justice³ while western laws focus on individual rights and due process. Balancing these systems is complex, requiring consideration of cultural traditions and human rights.⁴ The system has faced intense scrutiny regarding effectively addressing the root causes of delinquency and protecting young offenders. Key challenges include reconciling western juvenile justice concepts with local realities and infrastructure.⁵ Cultural context also poses unique difficulties in developing a culturally-sensitive system.⁶

Despite legal frameworks, implementations struggle with numerous challenges. Inadequate institutional support and resources hinder appropriate interventions and support.⁷ The system suffers from insufficient funding, limited infrastructure and shortage of specialized personnel such as judges, lawyers and social workers.⁸ Given implementation controversies and criticisms, this study aims to examine Nigeria's juvenile justice system. It will explore historical development, legal frameworks, challenges and reform avenues. By assessing strengths and

1 Child Rights Act of 2003

2 Children and Young Person's Act of 1958

3 Ajah, Linus, and Chukwudi Ugwuoke. "Challenges of Child Imprisonment in Nigeria: The Case of Child Prisoners." *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization*, vol. 75, 2017, pp. 78-88.

4 Silas, Oluwakemi. "Child Rights Act in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges." *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, vol. 1 no. 2, 2010, pp. 254-262.

5 Okpalaobi, Blessing, and Lucy Ekwueme. "Nigeria's Implementation of the Convention on the Rights of the Child." *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, vol. 5, no. 1, 2015, pp. 55-64.

6 Kabo, Patrick. "Challenges of Child Justice Administration in Kogi State, Nigeria." *International Journal of Innovative Legal & Political Studies*, vol. 10, no. 1, 2022, pp. 34-43.

7 Nwanna, Chinelo, and Mobolaji Ogunniran. "Perspectives of Social Welfare Officers on Implementation of the Lagos State Child's Rights Law." *International Journal of Criminal Justice Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 2, 2014, pp. 234-247.

8 Olowu, Dejo. "Protecting Children's Rights in the Muslim Context: Contemporary Discourses on Islamic Law, Children's Rights and Shariah." *Journal of Law, Religion and State*, vol. 6, no. 1, 2008, pp. 31-66.

weaknesses, insights will contribute to ongoing discourse on juvenile justice and provide guidance for policymakers and practitioners. Comprehensive analysis can help ensure juvenile rights protection and promote offender reintegration into society.⁹

The study employs a doctrinal research methodology, which involves comprehensively examining and analyzing primary legal sources such as relevant legislation, case laws, and international treaties and conventions ratified by Nigeria pertaining to juvenile justice. This includes the Child's Rights Act, 2003, Children and Young Persons Act 1958, Criminal Code Act, Penal Code Act, Administration of Criminal Justice Act 2015, important judicial pronouncements interpreting these laws, as well as international instruments like the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child. Through a qualitative approach, the research will systematically identify, categorize and discuss the key principles, frameworks, relationships, and issues arising from these primary materials to evaluate the national legal landscape regarding conformity with frameworks, implementation realities, and international obligations.

2. CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

i. Juvenile

The term "juvenile" derives its origins from the Latin word "juvenis" ("Juvenile"). In classical Latin, "juvenis" referred specifically to a young man who is in the phase of life between childhood and full adulthood.¹⁰ The Black's Law dictionary defines 'juvenile' as a "A young person; an individual under a statutorily designated age who is legally subject to parental control".¹¹

ii. Concept of Justice

The Black's Law Dictionary describes justice as "the fair and proper administration of laws."¹² Further, Lucas, explored the aspect of social justice in her work, underscoring that justice is not limited to legality but also extends to equality and fairness on a broader societal terrain. For Lucas, justice is intrinsically tied with liberation from exploitation and oppression, thus deviating from justice as a mere adherence to laws.¹³

⁹ Abass, Adeyemi. "Promoting Juvenile Justice and the Rights of the Child in Nigeria." *Journal of Politics and Law*, vol. 1, no. 3, 2008, pp. 78-86.

¹⁰ Cryer, Cornelia. *Juvenile Justice: The Historical Roots of Discretionary Justice in the Juvenile Court*. Vol. 84, no. 3, *Juvenile and Family Court Journal*, 1983, pp. 1-12.

¹¹ Black's Law Dictionary. Juvenile. 2019, <https://legal-dictionary.thefreedictionary.com/juvenile> accessed on 16 /1/2024.

¹² Garner, B. A. (Ed.). *Black's Law Dictionary*. West Group. 1999, available at <<https://legal-dictionary.thefreedictionary.com/justice>> accessed on 16 /1/2024.

¹³ Lucas, J. *Justice in Modern Society*. Palgrave Macmillan.2019, <https://books.google.co.uk/books/about/Justice_in_Modern_Society.html> accessed on 16 /1/2024.

iii. **Concept of Juvenile Justice**

Juvenile justice, as defined by Black's Law Dictionary, refers to the legal framework and the network of systems, policies, and procedures that are specifically designed to handle and respond to minors who have committed an offence.¹⁴ According to the report from the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child, the international juvenile justice standards require children to be treated in a manner that promotes their sense of dignity and worth. The objective is to reinforce the child's respect for the rights of others while considering their age and the desirability of their reintegration into society.¹⁵

iv. **Child Rights**

Child rights are the human rights of children. They are the rights that all children have, regardless of their race, religion, gender, or any other status. Child rights are important because they help to ensure that children have a healthy and happy childhood, and that they can grow up to be productive members of the society.¹⁶

3. NATURE AND SCOPE OF ADMINISTRATION OF JUVENILE JUSTICE

The juvenile justice system in Nigeria seeks to rehabilitate youthful offenders while upholding children's rights.¹⁷ It comprises law enforcement, juvenile/family courts, and correctional facilities working collaboratively under key legal frameworks.¹⁸ The Children and Young Persons Act of 1958 formed the initial basis, prescribing the minimum age of criminal responsibility as 7 years.¹⁹ Penal code also provides that "No act is an offence which is done: By a child under 7 years of age; By a child above 7 years of age but under 12 years of age who has not attained sufficient understanding to judge the nature and consequence of such act."²⁰ However, special dispensation is given to children during trial, with the aim of rehabilitation over retribution. Another key law is the Child's Rights Act of 2003. It strengthened protection

14 Garner, B. A. Black's Law Dictionary (9th Edition). Thomson Reuters. 2009, Available at <www.blacks_law_dictionary> accessed on 14 /1/2024.

15 UN Committee on the Rights of the Child, General Comment No. 10 (2007): Children's Rights in Juvenile Justice, 25 April 2007, CRC/C/GC/10. <www.children_read_more_society_justice.> accessed on 17 /1/2024.

16 UNICEF. 2011. Justice for Children: Ensuring Access for Children and their Representatives. UNICEF, New York. 2011

17 Akpan, E. E. Child protection legislation in Nigeria: An overview. International Social Work, 53(4), 2010. 531-543. <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0020872809360062>> accessed on 17 /1/2024.

18 Ogunremi, T. O. Challenges of juvenile justice administration in Nigeria: A criminological perspective. Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences, 5(20), 2014. 2453-2459. <[doi:10.5901/mjss.2014.v5n20p2453](https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2014.v5n20p2453)> accessed on 17 /1/2024.

19 Oluwafemi, O. Children's rights and justice for children in Nigeria. Journal of Sociological Research, 7(2), 2007. 57-66. <<https://doi.org/10.1080/21568607.2007.9725627>> accessed on 17 /1/2024.

20 Penal Code , Cap 89, Laws of Northern Nigeria, Section 50 (a).

for Nigerian children and promotion of their wellbeing. It emphasizes rehabilitation, restorative justice and reconciliatory measures for youths in conflict with the law.

In practice, the procedure begins with detection and apprehension of juvenile suspects by police child protection units or welfare committees.²¹ Juveniles are kept separately from adult criminals during detention. Police gather initial facts and petition child courts for appropriate charges. Petitions are then presented to specialized magistrates, judges or customary courts handling youth matters.²² A defence counsel is appointed if needed, with permission for parents/guardians to be present. Child-friendly procedures aim to reduce intimidation and understand circumstances leading to the offense.²³ If charges are established, pre-sentencing reports assess mitigating factors like remorse, family background, disability or substance abuse influencing behaviour. Courts consider non-custodial options first like probation, community service, counselling or fines before remand. Custodial sentences are a last resort.²⁴

Juvenile correctional homes subsequently implement court directives, prioritizing rehabilitation through vocational training, educational programs, skills development, medical/psychosocial support and reintegration preparation. These schemes aim to redirect minors from crime and prepare them as productive citizens.²⁵ However, inadequate infrastructure, human and financial resources undermine the system. High recidivism reflects institutional shortcomings.²⁶

4. LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR JUVENILE JUSTICE IN NIGERIA

i. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (As Amended)

The 1999 Nigerian Constitution contains some broad provisions that relate to children's rights. Section 33 guarantees the right to life for everyone including a child, prohibiting the intentional

21 Emumejaye, F. B. (2012). Challenges in the administration of juvenile justice in Nigeria. *US-China Law Review*, 9(5), 661-670.

22 Ogunremi, T. O. Challenges of juvenile justice administration in Nigeria: A criminological perspective. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(20), 2014, 2453-2459. <doi:10.5901/mjss.2014.v5n20p2453> accessed on 18 /1/2024.

23 Emumejaye, F. B. Challenges in the administration of juvenile justice in Nigeria. *US-China Law Review*, 9(5), 2012. 661-670.

24 Akpan, E. E. Child protection legislation in Nigeria: An overview. *International Social Work*, 53(4), 2010, 531–543. <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0020872809360062>> accessed on 18/1/2024.

25 Ogunremi, T. O. Challenges of juvenile justice administration in Nigeria: A criminological perspective. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(20), 2010, 2453-2459. <doi:10.5901/mjss.2014.v5n20p2453> accessed on 18 /1/2024.

26 Inokoba, P. K., & Ikudayisi, A. M. (2010). A study of recidivism among juvenile offenders in Port Harcourt maximum security custodial centre. *International Journal of Criminology and Sociology*, 1, 46-54.

deprivation of a child's life.²⁷ This provides a fundamental protection for children under the constitution. Section 34 further protects a child's inherent right to dignity, prohibiting any form of torture or inhuman and degrading treatment against everyone including a child.²⁸ This ensures children are treated with dignity and respect. Additionally, Section 42 prohibits discrimination against children on the basis of circumstances of birth.²⁹ This prevents children from being discriminated against in the enjoyment of their rights due to factors such as their parents' status or ethnicity.

Chapter II of the 1999 Nigerian Constitution outlines the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy. This chapter sets broad policy goals for the government to pursue, such as ensuring humane conditions and equality of rights for all citizens. By mentioning "all citizens", this includes protecting the rights of children as citizens. One of the policy directives in Section 18 relates to educational objectives. It mandates free, compulsory and universal primary education for children. It also aims to progressively reduce illiteracy rates.³⁰ This protects children's right to education. While Chapter II and Section 18 establish some protections for children's rights as policy goals, they are not judicially enforceable and do not amount to explicit legal rights.³¹

More importantly, these sections and the wider Constitution are largely silent on issues specifically pertaining to juvenile justice and the rights of children in conflict with the law. Key elements of an effective juvenile justice system like the minimum age of criminal responsibility and separation of juvenile offenders from adult criminals are not explicitly provided for. The absence of provisions dedicated to crafting a separate juvenile justice system catered to children's unique developmental needs and rights places them at risk of having their rights and vulnerabilities overlooked within the general criminal justice framework designed for adults.³² While acknowledging children's rights in policy, the Constitution fails to sufficiently define

27 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999, (As Amended), sec. 33

28 Ibid sec. 34

29 Ibid sec. 42

30 Ibid sec. 18

31 Odinkalu, Chidi Anselm. "Poor Justice: Corruption and the Lack of Accountability in the Nigerian Judiciary." Amnesty International, 2006.

32 UNICEF. Juvenile Justice in Nigeria. UNICEF, 2013. <[https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/media/296/file/Juvenile%20Justice%20in%20Nigeria%20\(English\).pdf](https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/media/296/file/Juvenile%20Justice%20in%20Nigeria%20(English).pdf)> Accessed 20 Oct. 2022.

and protect their rights within a dedicated juvenile justice system under the law. This leaves gaps and implementation challenges.³³

ii. The Child's Rights Act, 2003

The Child's Rights Act, 2003 provides a comprehensive framework for the Nigerian juvenile justice system. It adopts a child-centered restorative approach that prioritizes the welfare, rehabilitation and reintegration of children in conflict with the law. This represents a shift away from the previous punitive paradigm. Part XX of the Act establishes specialized mechanisms for child justice administration. Section 204 establishes the paramount of the child justice system for dealing with children in conflict with the law.³⁴ It mandates that children be subjected only to child-specific processes and not the ordinary adult criminal system. This upholds international standards for a separate juvenile justice system.

The Act emphasizes practices that uphold children's dignity and rights. Section 205 protects children's privacy while Section 207 provides for the specialization of police officers dealing with children.³⁵ Section 208 promotes the use of diversion and extra-judicial settlement to resolve matters involving children without resorting to formal court proceedings wherever possible.³⁶ Section 213 grants sole jurisdiction to the Family Court to try children in conflict with the law.³⁷ The Family Court is a specialized court established under Part XIII to handle all children's cases in a child-sensitive manner. Section 214 lays out children's rights to fair hearing and compliance with due process.³⁸ Section 215 provides guiding principles for adjudication focusing on the child's best interests and welfare.³⁹ Sections 217 to 223 outlined progressive procedures for handling children before the Family Court with an emphasis on restorative rather than punitive measures.⁴⁰ Children can be remanded to the care of their parents, guardians or fit persons, or to State care facilities under Section 218.⁴¹ Corrective

33 Okene, Victor I. "The Juvenile Justice Administration in Nigeria: An Overview of Emerging Issues." *Journal of Legal Pluralism and Unofficial Law*, vol. 45, no. 66, 2013, pp. 111-133.

34 Child Rights Act 2003, sec. 204

35 Ibid, sec. 205,207

36 Ibid, sec. 208

37 Ibid, sec. 213

38 Ibid, sec. 214

39 Ibid, sec. 215

40 Ibid, sec. 217-223

41 Ibid, sec. 218

orders prioritizing guidance, supervision and care rather than detention are to be issued under Sections 223 and 227.⁴² Detention is reserved as a last resort under Section 222.⁴³

Part XXI provides for robust supervision of children subject to non-custodial orders. Supervision officers are appointed under Section 239 to closely monitor children under community-based orders and support their rehabilitation and reintegration.⁴⁴ Default powers under Section 241 allow redirection to institutional facilities where supervision fails.⁴⁵ Part XXII regulates approved institutions for children. Children's attendance centers under Section 250 provide non-residential supportive measures while children's remand and correctional facilities aim to apply restorative justice and restitution principles under Section 236.⁴⁶ Post-release supervision under Section 259 ensures continued support.⁴⁷

The implementation of the Act's progressive juvenile justice provisions faces challenges. Long delays in family court proceedings contravene Section 154 which aims for expeditious hearings.⁴⁸ Overreliance on detention endures against the Act's emphasis on non-custodial options. Inadequate funding hinders the effective operation of the child-centered specialized structures established by the Act such as probation and aftercare services. Uneven commitment across States continues to compromise full domestication and implementation of the Act's provisions nationwide. As of 2020, only 24 of Nigeria's 36 states have formally domesticated the Child's Rights Act through state legislation.⁴⁹ Nonetheless, the Act has catalyzed significant reforms and enhanced protection for children in conflict with the law. Its provisions establish Nigeria as a leader in implementing international juvenile justice standards on the African continent if fully realized. Continued review and strengthening of implementation mechanisms will be vital to overcome obstacles and achieve the transformative vision of the Child Rights Act - establishing a truly restorative juvenile justice system with the child's welfare and rights as paramount considerations in all the states.

42 Ibid, sec. 223,227

43 Ibid, sec. 222

44 Ibid, sec. 239

45 Ibid, sec. 241

46 Ibid, sec. 250,236

47 Ibid, sec. 259

48 Ibid, sec. 154,

49 The states that have domesticated the Act are: Abia, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bayelsa, Benue, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Osun, Oyo, Plateau and Rivers.

iii. The Children and Young Person's Act (CYPA)

The current application of the Children and Young Person's Act (CYPA) in Nigeria is due to the non-adoption of the CRA in 11 states of the federation. In these states, the CYPA and other states' laws are applicable. Before the CRA was enacted, the CYPA was the main legislation dealing with child offenders. The law is divided into nine parts,⁵⁰ with Part 1 addressing preliminary issues and definitions. Part 2 focuses on bail issues related to child offenders under arrest and the establishment of juvenile courts. Part 3 deals with probation officers, while Parts 4 and 5 cover approved institutions and juveniles in need of care and attention. Part 6 outlines the contribution of parents/guardians towards the maintenance of juveniles. Parts 7, 8, and 9 address miscellaneous issues, including trading in children and the power to make regulations. It has been argued that the enactment of the CYPA, later adopted by states as the Children and Young Persons Law, and the use of special codes and procedures in juvenile matters were intended to protect children from the technical, cumbersome, and harsh nature of ordinary court procedures. This was a response to the need for a modern social justice system that aims to promote the welfare of the young and provide appropriate treatment for young offenders, as well as establish juvenile courts.

Consequently, it is appropriately contended that despite the availability of numerous criticisms and intellectual assaults against the juvenile system in the nation, the law and its implementation should not be simply rejected as remnants of the colonial era but rather should be recognized as some of the multifaceted legacies of the British colonial criminal justice system. This contention is supported by Brown's assertion that the legislation represents a rare instance of law collaborating with the disciplines of psychology and sociology to comprehend human behaviour.⁵¹ As for the arguments against the CYPA, it was appropriately highlighted that much of the criticism is not primarily rooted in the philosophical orientation of the imported model of juvenile justice system, but rather in the failure to enact comprehensive reforms in the applicable laws and enhance the administration of the system. This presents a significant challenge for Nigerian laws, particularly the CYPL, which has not been revised to adequately address the current needs of a juvenile offender in Nigeria.⁵²

iv. The Administration of Criminal Justice Act (ACJA 2015)

50 Alemika E. E. O. and Chukwuma, I. "Criminal Justice in Nigeria." *The Nigerian Criminal Justice System*. 2004 <<https://www.opensocietyfoundations.org/voices/criminal-justice-nigeria>> Accessed on 01/11/2023.

51 Badaiki, A.K. "Juvenile Justice Administration in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects." *The Law Review* 1, no. 1 (2008): 16-32.

52 Brown, J. "An Appraisal of Juvenile Justice Reforms in Nigeria." *Lagos Law Journal* 5 (1998): 82-102.

In relation to the administration of justice for child offenders, it can be argued that the ACJA is possibly the first federal law in the country to officially recognize the rights of children. This recognition is evident in section 452 (1),⁵³ where it stipulates that the provisions of the Child's Rights Act shall apply to child offenders,⁵⁴ with the exception of bail proceedings which are not addressed in the CRA. Instead, the child's situation in bail proceedings is governed by section 452 (2)⁵⁵ of the ACJA. This particular provision is noteworthy because it reinforces the necessity of implementing the CRA, thereby challenging the validity of certain traditional laws that pertain to children, such as the Criminal Code, Penal Code, and the Children and Young Persons Law.

The Administration of Criminal Justice Act is significant due to the outdated and non-compliant provisions it contains regarding child justice in relation to current international standards. In section 494 of the ACJA, a child is defined as an individual who has not yet reached the age of 18 years. In terms of the sentencing of child offenders, section 405 explicitly prohibits the imposition or recording of a death sentence against anyone below the age of 18 at the time the offense was committed. This provision aligns with the requirements set forth in section 221(1)(c) of the Child Rights Act (CRA) and the legal precedent established in the case of *Modupe v State*.⁵⁶ However, a drawback of the ACJA is that section 405 permits the sentencing of a child to life imprisonment as an alternative to the death penalty. This particular provision contradicts section 221(1)(a) of the CRA, which explicitly prohibits any form of child imprisonment. Nonetheless, section 405 does allow for the application of other alternatives listed in section 401 of the ACJA, such as prevention, restraint, rehabilitation, education, and retribution.

Sections 455-457 outline how children are to be treated gently and given special care at all stages of investigation and trial.⁵⁷ Police officers, prison officials and the courts are mandated to avoid exposing children to conditions or treatments that could negatively impact their physical and psychological development. Questioning of children also requires extra carefulness. Sections 458-460 confer powers on the courts to request probation or reform school reports on children, adjourn hearings and order community service or approve school or borstal training as alternatives to imprisonment.⁵⁸ This emphasizes rehabilitation over

53 The Administration of Criminal Justice Act (ACJA 2015), sec. 452(1)

54 Ibid.452(2)

55 ibid

56 *Modupe v state.*(1988) 4 NWLR (pt. 87) 130

57 ACJA, 2015, sec.455 - 457

58 Ibid, 458 - 460

punishment for juvenile offenders. Approval of the Attorney General is needed before a child can be sentenced to imprisonment as a last resort. To further protect children, section 461 bars publishing details that reveal their identities in legal proceedings.⁵⁹ Disclosure of names, schools, addresses or images is prohibited. This is aimed at avoiding stigma and enabling social reintegration.

v. The Violence against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015

The primary statute governing the administration of child and juvenile justice under the second set of domestic laws examined in this study is the Violence against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015. The CYPA was the main piece of legislation pertaining to juvenile offenders before the CRA was passed. The law's language is generally separated into nine sections. Preliminary issues (definitions) are covered in Part 1, juvenile court constitution and bail issues pertaining to underage offenders are covered in Part 2, and probation officials are covered in Part 3. Parts 4 and 5 deal with approved institutions and juveniles in need of care, while Part 6 allows parents and guardians to contribute to the maintenance of their minor children. Parts 7, 8, and 9 address various issues, including the trading of children and the authority to make regulations.⁶⁰

The Children and Young Persons Act was enacted in response to the need for a modern social justice system, with the goal of providing "...for the welfare of the young and the treatment of young offenders and for the establishment of juvenile courts." States later adopted the CYPL, and the application of special codes and procedure in juvenile matters was meant to protect the child from the highly technical, laborious, and harsh nature of procedure applied in ordinary courts. Consequently, it was legitimately asserted that despite the fact that the juvenile system in the nation is subject to numerous critiques and intellectual attacks, the legislation and the way it is implemented.⁶¹ Brown's claim that the legislation is a unique instance of law interacting with psychology and sociology the sciences that study human behavior supports this line of reasoning.⁶² It was correctly noted in response to the arguments made against the CYPA that a large portion of the criticism centres on the inability to significantly alter the pertinent legislation and enhance the system's management rather than the imported juvenile justice system's philosophical tenets. This is a significant issue with Nigerian legislation, especially the CYPL, which has not been updated to address the needs of juvenile offenders in the country today.

59 Ibid, 461

60 Ibid

61 Badaiki, A.K. "Juvenile Justice Administration in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects." *The Law Review* 1, no. 1 (2008): 16-32.

62 Brown, Sheila. *Understanding youth and crime: listening to youth?*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK), 2005.

vi. The Penal Code

The Penal Code Act is applicable to all states in the northern region of Nigeria. The PCA serves to safeguard the child from the point of conception, as it is deemed unlawful to terminate the life of an unborn child through the act of abortion. This legislation acknowledges the entitlements of the unborn child.⁶³ The responsibility of fulfilling the fundamental requirements for survival, development, and sustenance of children under the age of 14 lies with their parents, guardians, or legal custodians.

Section 71 of the Penal Code states that an individual who is accused of committing an offense after their seventh but before their eighteenth, if found guilty, must be handled pursuant to the procedures outlined in the Children and Young Persons Act.⁶⁴ The Sharia Penal Code Laws that have been implemented in some northern Nigerian states likely do not properly account for children's rights as defined by the Child's Rights Act, as their concept of rights differs from international standards.

vii. The Criminal Code

The Criminal Code Act (CCA) is applicable to the southern region of Nigeria, and it contains provisions aimed at safeguarding the welfare of children. According to the Criminal Code Act, children below the age of 7 are considered incapable of committing an offense.⁶⁵ However, children between the ages of 7 and 12 can be held criminally accountable if it can be proven that they fully comprehend the nature and consequences of their actions.⁶⁶ Furthermore, children aged 12 to 18 can be charged for their criminal acts or omissions but are not subject to prosecution within the adult justice system. Instead, they are dealt with in accordance with the Children and Young Persons Law (CYPL). It is important to note that any discrepancies in the age of the child as defined in the CYPL compared to the Child's Right Act which are subject to section 274 of the CRA.

According to section 39 of the Criminal Code, an offender under the age of 17 cannot be sentenced to death, as was decided in the case of *Guobadia v State*.⁶⁷ Instead of the death penalty, such young offenders will be detained at the discretion of the President. This highlights the reliance on institutionalization, similar to the provisions of the Children and Young Persons Act. However, it also implies that individuals over 17 but still considered children under the current law could potentially face imprisonment, rather than just detention, for their offenses.

63 The Penal Code, section 232.

64 Children and Young Persons Act. Cap. C50 L.F.N. 2004. Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (Revised Edition).

65 Criminal code, Section , 18

66 Ibid sec. 30

67 *Guobadia v state* (sc 295/2002) [2004] 24 (20 February 2004)

So, while the death penalty is prohibited for the very young, the law allows for the imprisonment of older juveniles, going against international standards of treating all persons under 18 as children.

2. INTERNATIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR JUVENILE JUSTICE

i. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC)

The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) lays out key principles for the administration of juvenile justice according to international law. It establishes that the CRC is the foremost international instrument for protecting children's rights. Specifically, Articles 37 and 40 relate to justice for children in conflict with the law. Article 1 defines a child as any person under 18 years of age, unless domestic law allows for earlier attainment of majority.⁶⁸ Critically, Article 3(1) dictates that the best interests of the child must be the primary consideration in all matters concerning them. Article 37 prohibits torture, cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment of children, as well as capital punishment or life imprisonment without the possibility of release for those less than 18 years old. Further, Article 37(b) prohibits the unlawful or arbitrary deprivation of a child's liberty. It requires that arrest, detention or imprisonment of a child be used only as an absolute last resort and for the shortest appropriate period of time. Additionally, Article 37(c) stipulates that deprived children must be treated with humanity and separated from adults, unless deemed not in their best interest. These articles establish the core humanitarian and rights-based principles for how children in conflict with the law should be treated.⁶⁹

Article 40 outlines key due process rights for children in conflict with the law. Article 40(1) states that a child accused of an offence should be treated with dignity, respecting their human rights and taking into account their age, with the aim of reintegrating them productively into the society. Article 40(2)(a) stipulates that children can only be charged with offences prohibited at the time of commission under domestic or international law. Article 40(2)(b) establishes a child's entitlement to a fair and just trial process, including the rights to be presumed innocent, promptly informed of charges, have their case determined without undue delay by an independent and impartial judicial body in a fair hearing attended by legal assistance. Children also have the right not to self-incriminate, examine witnesses, have access to an interpreter if needed, and have their privacy respected throughout legal proceedings. This

68 United Nations General Assembly. Convention on the Rights of the Child. Treaty Series, vol. 1577, 1989

69 Santos, P.M. "Justice for Children: The United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice and Parallel Processes." *Children, Youth and Environments*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2003, pp. 41-54.

provision guarantees children in conflict with the law receive full protection of fair trial rights and humane, rehabilitative treatment from authorities and the justice system.⁷⁰

Article 40(3) obligates states to establish laws, procedures, authorities and institutions specifically for children engaged with the criminal justice system. It mandates setting a minimum age of criminal responsibility below which children are deemed legally incapable of committing an offence. States must also devise measures to handle such young lawbreakers without judicial proceedings, while fully respecting human rights and legal safeguards. Article 40(4) prioritizes alternative measures to court processes. It lists options like care orders, supervision, counselling, probation, foster care, education and vocational programs. The provision assures other non-institutional alternatives exist to ensure the child's well-being and that any measures are proportionate to both the offense and the unique circumstances of the young person. Together, these sections require specialized, extrajudicial responses for child offenders that promote welfare, rehabilitation and proportional treatment outside of formal court involvement whenever appropriate.

The effective implementation of Articles 37-40 of the CRC regarding juvenile justice is aided by three key UN instruments. The first is the United Nations Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (the Beijing Rules), which predate and informed the CRC. Article 40(4) of the CRC reinforces Rule 5 of the Beijing Rules that the overarching aims of juvenile justice are promotion of the young person's well-being and ensuring any response is proportionate to both the offense and the unique circumstances of the offender. This "principle of proportionality" curbs punitive sanctions by requiring the reaction to be considerate of personal factors like social status, family situation, harm caused, and the child's willingness to make amends or reform. In sum, these rules emphasize that dealing with young lawbreakers must account for their individual life experiences and aim for rehabilitation over retribution, in line with the CRC's stance of prioritizing the welfare of the child throughout the justice process.⁷¹

70 Hammarberg, T. "Juvenile Justice and Children's Rights." In *The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child: A Study of Legal Implementation*, edited by Rikke Nørgaard and Gerison Lansdown, Dartmouth, 1994, pp. 129-152

71 Doek, J. E. "The CRC and Juvenile Justice." In *A Commentary on the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child*, edited by Detrick Sharon, Martin Otto et al., Martinus Nijhoff, 1999, pp. 203-243.

ii. The United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for The Administration of Juvenile Justice (Beijing rules 1985)

The Beijing Rules, adopted by the UN in 1985, establishes international standards for the proper administration of juvenile justice.⁷² They aim to promote the well-being of juvenile offenders in accordance with their status as minors and to reinforce their reintegration and assumed role as productive members of the society. The Rules outline procedures for all aspects of the juvenile justice process, including pre-trial detention, diversion, and alternatives to institutionalization. They stress that deprivation of liberty should only be used as a last resort. The Rules also emphasize special protections for juveniles, such as the presumption of innocence, the right to privacy, and protection from self-incrimination. They call for separate facilities and proceedings for children, with interdisciplinary personnel trained in child development and legal rights. If followed, the Beijing Rules provide UN member states with a framework for administering a justice system suitable for juveniles' varied needs and focused on rehabilitation over punishment.⁷³

iii. The United Nations Guidelines for The Prevention of Juvenile Delinquency (Riyadh Guidelines 2010)

The Riyadh Guidelines adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1990 provide the global framework for promoting best practices in the field of juvenile justice.⁷⁴ They emphasize using non-judicial measures over formal legal proceedings for children accused of crimes, wherever suitable.⁷⁵ The guidelines stress that the age of criminal culpability should not be too low and that severe adult penalties must not be imposed on young offenders.⁷⁶ Community-based programs are preferred under the Riyadh Guidelines to support rehabilitation and reintegration rather than incarceration.⁷⁷ States are advised to respect due process rights for children in conflict with the law during all stages of investigation and adjudication.⁷⁸ The guidelines also highlight the need for preventative interventions tailored to local social and economic

72 United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice ("The Beijing Rules"). Resolution 40/33, adopted 29 November 1985.

73 Ibid

74 United Nations General Assembly. Guidelines for the Prevention of Juvenile Delinquency (The Riyadh Guidelines). Resolution 45/112, adopted 14 December 1990.

75 Steiner, H. "The UN Standards and Norms in Juvenile Justice." In *Juvenile Justice Systems: International Perspectives*, edited by Barry C. Feld and Don C. Gibbons, Roxbury Publishing Company, 2009.

76 Goldson, B. "Children's Imprisonment: Universality, exceptionalism and criminalisation." In *Children and International Law: The Right of the Child in a Globalized World*, edited by Aoife Nolan, HART Publishing, 2019, pp. 133-152.

77 Kilkelly, U. "Youth Justice and Children's Rights: Measuring Compliance with International Standards." *Youth Justice* 10, no. 2 (2010): 151-167.

78 Omoruyi, O. "Human Right of the Child in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects." *Journal of Politics and Law* 6, no. 4 (2013): 113.

conditions. Nations are encouraged to undertake research and compile data on effective strategies for curbing juvenile delinquency according to the Riyadh Guidelines.⁷⁹ They remain the foremost international reference for legal systems to ensure specialized, rights-compliant treatment of children in the justice system.

iv. The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child (ACRWC)

The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child also establishes standards for juvenile justice administration at the regional level. Article 17(1) provides that every child accused or convicted of an offense has the right to special treatment conducted in a manner consistent with preserving their dignity and worth, while reinforcing respect for others' rights and freedoms. It prohibits torture or degrading treatment against children deprived of liberty under Article 17(2), requiring their separation from adults in detention. Such children are also entitled to fair, speedy hearings by an impartial tribunal and the right to appeal if found guilty.⁸⁰ Critically, Article 17(3) maintains that the overarching aim in dealing with any child engaged in the justice system, whether during trial or upon conviction, shall be their reformation, reintegration into their family, and social rehabilitation. The Charter therefore mirrors key CRC principles like the imperative of humane, individualized and rehabilitative treatment of young people within regional judicial processes in Africa.⁸¹

While international instruments have established commendable protections for child offenders, significant challenges remain in implementing these standards effectively. A major issue worldwide, including in Nigeria, is the problem of rising juvenile delinquency as more young people engage in criminal acts such as theft, rape, and cybercrimes.⁸² Additionally, millions of children are incarcerated globally each year without committing serious offenses - they are often detained for so-called "non-criminal status offenses" like truancy, vagrancy, or homelessness that would not be criminal if perpetrated by adults. This amounts to discriminatory treatment that should be abolished, as such behaviors are better viewed as normal developmental stages of childhood rather than criminal behaviors.⁸³ Further, over-reliance on detention as a punitive response contradicts international rules specifying it should

⁷⁹ Omoruyi, O. "Human Right of the Child in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects." *Journal of Politics and Law* 6, no. 4 (2013): 113.

⁸⁰ Organization of African Unity (OAU). *African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child*. CAB/LEG/24.9/49, 1990.

⁸¹ Armstrong, R. "Justice for Children in Conflict with the Law: Promoting the African Juvenile Justice Standards." *African Child Policy Forum*, 2011.

⁸² Iro, U.E., and Emma U. "Rising crimes among teenagers in Calabar, Nigeria: causes, consequences and control." *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth* 24, no. 2 (2019): 188-197.

⁸³ Dauda, S. "Overcriminalization of Juvenile status offenses and relevant international standards: The case of Nigeria." *Children and Youth Services Review* 77 (2017): 227-233.

only be used as an absolute last resort. In many places including Nigeria, detention is still commonly applied as the first option for juvenile offenders.⁸⁴ Considerable work is still needed to address issues like growing juvenile crime, over-criminalization of common child actions, and under-utilization of community-based alternatives to custody in line with a rehabilitative model of juvenile justice advocated globally.

3. INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR JUVENILE JUSTICE IN NIGERIA

i. Nigeria Police Force

The Nigeria Police Force stems from the 1999 constitution of Nigeria, which established it as a national police force and enshrines fundamental human rights.⁸⁵ The Police Act of 2020 is the primary legislation dictating the organization, functions, and responsibilities of the police. It emphasizes community-oriented policing through collaboration with citizens.⁸⁶ The legal framework for policing is extensive. The Criminal and Penal Codes provide definitions and punishments of offenses to guide investigations. The Administration of Criminal Justice Act lays out arrest, detention, investigation and trial procedures to ensure due process.⁸⁷

For juvenile justice, the key law is the 2003 Child Rights Act, which domesticates the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child. It mandates strict procedural safeguards when arresting, detaining or questioning minors, such as promptly informing parents/guardians and treating young suspects in an age-appropriate manner. Compliance is monitored by the Children's Rights Implementation Committee. State laws like Lagos' Children and Young Persons Law outline police powers and protocols for handling juvenile cases. The Criminal Procedure Act and Police Act further provide guidance on investigative procedures involving accused minors.⁸⁸ This blended framework of domestic and international law aims to balance enforcement with children's best interests.⁸⁹ However, police often lack skills to properly handle juveniles according to these protocols.⁹⁰ There have been cases of publishing children's photos or showing them on TV with adults, violating laws protecting minors.⁹¹ Such practices

⁸⁴ Arnaudo, G. et al. "Children's rights behind bars: tracking progress on the UN Global Study on children deprived of liberty." *International Journal of Children's Rights* 27.4 (2019): 704-740.

⁸⁵ **Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) part III, sec. 214**

⁸⁶ **Police Act, 2020, sec.4,6,8**

⁸⁷ Durojaye, E. and Morolake O. "The Administration of Criminal Justice Act, 2015 and the Right to a Fair Trial in Nigeria." *African Human Rights Law Journal* 18, no. 2 (2018): 334-356.

⁸⁷ Child Rights Act. 2003. Law of the Federation of Nigeria.

⁸⁸ **Police Act, 2020**

⁸⁹ United Nations General Assembly. *United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice*. Resolution 40/33. 1985.

⁹⁰ Maguire, Ed, et al. "Comparative Perspectives on Juvenile Justice Reform in Lagos, Nigeria." *International Journal of Comparative and Applied Criminal Justice*, vol. 40, no. 4, 2016, pp. 329-348.

⁹¹ Okagbue, Ifeanyi. "Juvenile Justice Reforms and the Protection of Children's Rights in Nigeria." *African Journal of Criminology and Justice Studies*, vol. 11, no. 1, 2019, pp. 39-59.

can negatively impact psychology, especially during arrest.⁹² This fails to meet statutory and treaty requirements for upholding procedural safeguards for juveniles in both policy and practice. Improved training is still needed.⁹³

ii. Judicial Institution

The Nigerian juvenile justice system comprises courts specifically handling youth cases, demonstrating a legal framework focused on juvenile criminal justice.⁹⁴ The primary juvenile court is governed by the Children and Young Persons Act,⁹⁵ aiming to protect children's rights rather than purely punish through flexible, diversionary procedures. Comparatively, Nigerian juvenile courts historically preferred custodial institutions based on rehabilitation over probation or fines.

Family Courts were established in 2003 under the Child Rights Act with civil and criminal jurisdiction over family matters including child justice administration.⁹⁶ The philosophy is therapeutic jurisprudence - intervening well with public accountability to heal and preserve families.⁹⁷ Family Courts operate at magistrate and high court levels, with appeals to high court. They are guided by child-sensitive rights and novel principles in the Child Rights Act.

Child offenders have rights to legal representation due to inability to self-represent. They have fair, "child-friendly" hearings respecting their "best interests" and ability to participate. Family Courts use custodial (e.g. detention, institutions) and non-custodial (e.g. supervision, guardianship) disposition methods. Presently over ten states have established Family Courts with dedicated facilities and procedural frameworks. Trainings aim to ground judicial officers in the philosophy. The Committee on the Rights of the Child recommends all states establish adequately resourced Family Courts.⁹⁸

iii. Borstal Training Institutes, Approved Schools and Remand Homes

Borstal institutions in Nigeria were established to rehabilitate troubled youth through education, skills training, and character development. They aim to reform juveniles and

92 Goldson, Barry, and John Muncie. "Towards a Global 'Child Friendly' Juvenile Justice?" *International Journal of Law, Policy and the Family*, vol. 26, no. 2, 2012, pp. 147-169.

93 UNICEF. 2011. *Justice for Children: Ensuring Access for Children and their Representatives*. UNICEF, New York. 2011

94 Adele, J.O. *The Police and Law Enforcement in Nigeria*. In Okonkwo et al (Eds.), *Contemporary Issues on the Administration of Criminal Justice in Nigeria*, 2002, (pp. 127-148). Aba, Nigeria: Legal Research and Resource Development Centre.

95 Children and Young Persons Act. Cap. C50 LFN 2004.

96 Child Rights Act, 2003

97 Caleb, R. P. *An Appraisal of the Rights and Welfare of the Nigerian Child in Conflict with the Law*. Unpublished PhD Thesis. Ibadan: University of Ibadan. 2003

98 Committee on the Rights of the Child. *Concluding Observations on the Combined Third to Fifth Periodic Reports of Nigeria*, 2015. CRC/C/NGA/CO/3

reintegrate them as productive community members.⁹⁹ Borstals fall under the Nigerian Prisons Service and legally target young offenders who have committed less serious crimes.¹⁰⁰ Originally, Nigeria only had two borstals.¹⁰¹ Currently, the three operational institutions—in Kaduna, Ilorin, and Abeokuta—often face overcrowding issues. For example, the Kaduna borstal held over 600 inmates in its 200-person facility in 2013.¹⁰² There is potential for growing numbers of youth in the justice system as well.¹⁰³

However, borstals struggle in their rehabilitation goals due to lack of facilities and deteriorating conditions in existing ones. This undermines protections for children in custody and risks worsening criminal behaviours.¹⁰⁴ Resources are insufficient despite rising juvenile crimes and delinquency rates. As a result, the justice system mixes young offenders with adults, violating the non-imprisonment of children policy. Overcrowding, boredom and powerlessness in prisons foster gang formation among inmates and potentially reinforce criminality.¹⁰⁵ Inadequate healthcare further compounds these challenges.¹⁰⁶ Studies find high prevalence of undetected mental illness among borstal residents,¹⁰⁷ highlighting urgent need within the juvenile justice system.¹⁰⁸

4. CHALLENGES OF THE NIGERIAN JUVENILE JUSTICE

- i. **Alignment with International Standards:** Nigeria's legal framework for juvenile justice aligns with international standards like the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child through laws like the Child's Rights Act, 2003. However, significant challenges exist in implementing these protections in practice.¹⁰⁹

99 Borstal Institutions and Remand Centers Act LFN of 2004. Federal Government of Nigeria, 2004.

100 Nigeria Prisons Service. "About Us." Nigeria Prisons Service, 2014, <https://www.prisons.gov.ng/about-us/>. Accessed 23 Apr. 2023.

101 Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies. "Study on Juvenile Justice Administration in Nigeria." Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, 1996.

102 Sa'ad, Abubakar Umar. "Institutional Factors Affecting Reformation and Rehabilitation of Juveniles at the Borstal Training Institutions in Nigeria." *Social and Management Research Journal*, vol. 11, no. 1, 2014, pp. 95-108.

103 Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies. "Study on Juvenile Justice Administration in Nigeria." Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, 1996.

104 Madaki, John Sunday. "A Critical Examination of the Causative Factors of Juvenile Delinquency in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State, Nigeria." *African Research Review*, vol. 8, no. 4, 2014, pp. 208-225.

105 Milner, E. "The Borstal System." *Howard Journal of Criminal Justice*, vol. 11, no. 3, 1972, pp. 209-215.

106 Issa, Babandi A., and Sina Aderinto. "Psychiatric Morbidity among Borstal Inmates in Kaduna, Nigeria." *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, vol. 52, no. 4, 2008, pp. 455-461.

107 Ibid

108 Madaki, John Sunday. "A Critical Examination of the Causative Factors of Juvenile Delinquency in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State, Nigeria." *African Research Review*, vol. 8, no. 4, 2014, pp. 208-225.

109 Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies. "Study on Juvenile Justice Administration in Nigeria." Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, 1996.

- ii. Implementation challenge: The primary challenge for Nigeria's juvenile justice system is implementing existing legal protections due to gaps between law and practice. Children face harsh conditions despite laws aiming to protect their rights and welfare. Varying implementation across states due to uneven domestication of acts like the Child's Rights Act undermines a uniform national system. Resource constraints, cultural norms, weak coordination of agencies, and lack of reform further impede sound implementation of provisions that could otherwise benefit vulnerable youths.¹¹⁰
- iii. **Healthcare, Educational Resources, and Recreational Facilities Challenges:** Inadequate healthcare, education, and recreation limit attention to physical and mental health needs, intellectual development, and behavior modification essential for rehabilitation and reentry into society. Poor sanitation, overcrowding, and lack of mental healthcare increase disease risk. Limited educational resources diminish literacy and skills, hindering post-release prospects.¹¹¹
- iv. **Challenges of Merging Juvenile and adult offenders:** Amalgamating juvenile and adult offenders in Nigeria's correctional facilities undermines international standards and increases recidivism among youths. In a 2009 study, Alemika and Chukwuma found youth exposed to harsh adult prisons had a recidivism rate of over 60%, compared to less than 20% for those in juvenile centers.¹¹² A 2013 study by Alemika also showed combined facilities led to higher rates of abuse, interrupted education, and declining mental health among 200 juveniles across six centers, correlating with 80% reoffending within three years.¹¹³
- v. **Corruption:** Corruption and lack of accountability severely undermine fair procedures and protections for children in conflict with the law in Nigeria. Without effective oversight, corruption has permeated various aspects of the juvenile justice system.
- vi. **Pre-Trial Delays and Overreliance on Incarceration**
The issues of pre-trial delays and overreliance on incarceration pose significant challenges to the juvenile justice system in Nigeria. Prolonged pre-trial detention,

110 Alemika, E.O.E. and Chukwuma, I.C. Punishment and Social Reintegration of Juvenile Offenders in Nigeria. *The British Journal of Criminology*, 49(3), 2019, pp.342-359.

111 Amucheazi, Emma-Charity O., and Amaka Eze. "Juvenile Detention Facilities in Nigeria: A Review of Rehabilitation Outcomes and Challenges." *International Journal of Adolescent Medicine and Health*, vol. 21, no. 3, Dec. 2009, pp. 425–435. EBSCOhost, doi:10.1515/IJAMH.2009.21.3.425. Accessed Date.

112 Alemika, E.O.E. and Chukwuma, I.C. Punishment and Social Reintegration of Juvenile Offenders in Nigeria. *The British Journal of Criminology*, 49(3), 2009, pp.342-359.

113 Alemika, E. O. Examination of Living Conditions and Rehabilitation Outcomes in Nigerian Youth Custodial Centers. Kuwait Programme on Development, Governance and Globalisation in the Gulf States. 2013.

sometimes lasting years, violates international law by subjecting minors to damaging conditions in severely overcrowded facilities without adequate rehabilitation.¹¹⁴

vii. Cultural Practices and Stigmatization

The intersection of cultural practices and juvenile justice presents a set of unique challenges.¹¹⁵ Juvenile justice in Nigeria struggles with the domination of cultural norms. These norms encourage the demonisation and marginalisation of children in conflict with the law rather than rehabilitating them and reintegrating them back into society.¹¹⁶

viii. Weak Monitoring and Accountability: The juvenile justice system in Nigeria is characterised by weak monitoring and accountability, presenting a significant challenge to the enforcement of child rights and the proper development and reintegration into society of juvenile offenders.¹¹⁷

ix. Inadequate Data Collection and Research: Inadequate data collection and research present major hurdles to effective reforms in Nigeria's juvenile justice system. Without accurate data, policymaking becomes devoid of its essence, leading to misguided regulations often not tailored to the peculiarities of the populace they intend to serve.¹¹⁸

5. PROSPECTS OF THE NIGERIAN JUVENILE JUSTICE

i. Comprehensive Review of Existing Juvenile Justice Laws: Comprehensive review and reforming Nigeria's legal framework presents the prospect of better aligning domestic laws with international juvenile justice standards.¹¹⁹ A thorough examination of statutes could identify gaps between national provisions and norms outlined in conventions like the UNCRC.¹²⁰

ii. Improving Coordination between Agencies Involved in Administering Juvenile Justice:

¹¹⁴ United Nations Children's Fund. "Situation Analysis of Children in Nigeria." Abuja: UNICEF, 2017.

¹¹⁵ Elonu, O.C., and Victor, M.U. "Reintegrating Socially Deviant Youths through the Influence of Family and Community: A Sociological Analysis." *African Journal of Criminology and Justice Studies* 11, no. 2 (2019): 95-111. Rights Watch. *Juvenile Justice Reform in Nigeria*. New York: Human Rights Watch, 2013.

¹¹⁶ Ademola, S. "The Demonization of Children in Conflict with the Law: a Challenge for Juvenile Justice in Nigeria." *African Studies Quarterly* 15, no. 2 (2015).

¹¹⁷ Jjeoma, O. and Donatus I. "The State of the Nigerian Child: Political Economy of Rights, Denials and Development Deficits." Dhillon Publishing, 2014.

¹¹⁸ Smith, R. "Improving Evidence-Based Policy Making in Nigeria." International Growth Centre, 2017.

¹¹⁹ Decker, S. M. "Juvenile Justice Reform in Nigeria: A Historical Overview." *Leiden Journal of International Law*, vol. 34, no. 4, 2021, pp. 695-717.

¹²⁰ United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC). 1989. <<https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/crc.aspx>> Accessed Date 18/1/2024

Improving coordination between agencies involved in administering juvenile justice presents several prospects for more effective case management and strengthened accountability.

- iii. Increasing Funding and Resources:** Allocating increased funding to Nigeria's juvenile justice system presents numerous prospects for strengthening infrastructure and services. Additional budgetary support holds potential to transform existing sub-par detention facilities that often exacerbate socio-economic risks for vulnerable children.
- iv. Developing robust non-custodial, Community-based Diversion:** Developing robust non-custodial, community-based diversion programs presents various prospects to reform Nigeria's over-reliant incarceration approach for juvenile offenders.
- v. Developing Robust Data Collection Systems:** Investing in robust data collection systems presents several promising prospects for strengthening evidence-based reforms in Nigeria's juvenile justice process. A centralized digital case management platform could prospectively allow efficient tracking of key indicators and monitoring of individual progress reports.
- vi. Establishing an Independent Oversight Body**

Creating an autonomous oversight body with a legislative mandate holds potential prospects for enhanced enforcement of child rights protections and welfare standards in juvenile facilities.¹²¹ Empowering the body to conduct unannounced inspections of all detention centres could help uncover violations, analyze root causes, and ensure timely resolution.
- vii. Training law enforcement, Judicial and welfare officers:** Launching extensive, mandatory training programs for frontline officers holds significant prospects to reform practices and ensure a rights-based approach.
- viii. Improving Access to Legal Aid and Social Services:** Enhancing availability of quality legal aid holds prospects to significantly reform children's access to fair trial rights from the initial investigation stages onwards. Partnering with pro bono lawyers and paralegal organizations presents avenues to provide counselling at police stations, advice on case building, and expert representation during court proceedings.

¹²¹ UNICEF. "Justice For Children." *Juvenile Justice Systems, A Survey of Services for Children in Conflict with the Law*, 2001.

6. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This research identified several key findings regarding Nigeria's juvenile justice system. The system has undergone changes over time, transitioning from a punitive colonial model to a more rehabilitative approach in line with the Child's Rights Act and international standards. However, full implementation of reformed policies in practice continues to face obstacles. While the legal framework aims to uphold children's rights and due process, there are doubts about the extent to which these are realized. Effective implementation is hindered by challenges such as limited resources, inadequate training of personnel handling juvenile offenders, and broader issues in the criminal justice system. These challenges undermine attaining the desired protection of children's rights envisioned in legislation. Insufficient healthcare, education, and recreation in juvenile detention centres negatively impact the rehabilitation and welfare of young offenders. Without adequate access to these services and programs, juveniles find it difficult to acquire skills for successful reintegration post-release. The common practice of merging juvenile and adult populations in correctional facilities was also found to potentially increase recidivism rates by exposing the children to harmful influences. Finally, corruption and lack of accountability were seen to undermine fair procedures and protections for child offenders. This poses challenges to an equitable juvenile justice process. While reforms have occurred, fully implementing children's rights in practical application remains an ongoing issue due to obstacles relating to resources, training, oversight, and merging of juvenile offenders with adult systems.

7. CONCLUSION

This research work provided a thorough examination of the key legal frameworks governing juvenile justice in Nigeria. It began by conceptualizing important terms related to juveniles, juvenile justice, and child rights. This helped establish a common understanding of the domain being explored. The work then analyzed Nigeria's legal framework for juvenile justice, including several statutes such as the Child Rights Act, Criminal Code Act, and Penal Code. It found that while these laws aim to uphold international standards on children's rights, challenges remain regarding their practical implementation and alignment with UN guidelines. Factors like limited resources, regional disparities, and lack of accountability hamper full compliance.¹²² It concluded that while these lenses once shaped Nigeria's responses, contemporary realities necessitate revising assumptions to better address modern root causes

¹²² Uche, C., Juvenile justice administration in Nigeria: Progress, problems and prospects. *African Journal of Criminology and Justice Studies*, 2017. 10(1), pp.151-172.

of delinquency in areas like poverty, lack of opportunity, substance abuse and violence. Overall, this research presented a comprehensive picture of Nigeria's juvenile justice system, illuminating progress but also various implementation gaps hindering full alignment with international standards and rehabilitation objectives. Continued reforms are still needed to strengthen legal provisions, resource allocation, training, coordination, data collection, and oversight mechanisms.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the research work, here are some recommendations to strengthen the juvenile justice system in Nigeria:

i. Legal and Policy Reforms

There is a need for ongoing legal and policy reforms to strengthen Nigeria's juvenile justice framework. A new legislation should be enacted to address specific issues or gaps within the existing legal framework that allow for violations of child rights protections.

ii. Institutional Reforms

The research found limited access to healthcare, education and recreation within juvenile detention centres hinders rehabilitation. The government must allocate greater funding and material resources to these facilities to improve conditions and services.

iii. Community Engagement and Prevention

Active community engagement and preventive interventions are necessary to curb delinquency and recidivism over the long term. The government must foster collaborative partnerships between stakeholders like social welfare agencies, NGOs, schools, religious organizations and families to jointly address the underlying socioeconomic factors driving youth crime.¹²³

123 Kempf-Leonard, K., and Sontheimer, H. Introduction. In K. Kempf-Leonard, C. E. Pope, & W. Feyerherm (Eds.), *Minorities in juvenile justice*, 1997, (pp. 1–12). Sage